

MAJOR RISKS FACED BY STREET KIDS IN UYO METROPOLIS, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The street kids' phenomenon is a worldwide social and environmental menace relating to the faulty upbringing, neglect and poor welfare for certain groups of children all around the world. This research assessed the major risks facing street kids in the Uyo metropolis in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The Social Constructivism theory as explained by Lev Vygotsky was adopted as a theoretical framework. A survey research design was adopted for the study. This study was conducted in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample size considered for the study through Taro Yamane's formula was 150, but a total of 120 questionnaires were returned from the field which was the instrument for data collection. Data was analysed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) denoted by 'r'. The findings of the study show that Street kids dwell in an environment of hostility, they are neglected by members of the public, they often lack proper parental guidance, the street kids are most especially harmed by harsh physical conditions, violence and harassment, exploitation, absorption into criminal networks and denial to education that will equip them to have a better life. Based on findings, researchers among others recommended that government need to prioritize the development and implementation of comprehensive social welfare programs aimed at addressing the root causes of child vulnerability. This includes initiatives to alleviate poverty, provide access to education, healthcare, and affordable housing and support families in crisis.

Keywords: Risk, Street kids, Uyo, and Social Constructivism

INTRODUCTION

The street kids' phenomenon is a worldwide social and environmental menace relating to the faulty upbringing, neglect and poor welfare for certain groups of children all around the world. While such children are called *Street Children* in some parts of the world, they are called "*homeless Children*", in Western Europe (Basu, and Tzannatos, 2003) that is, they either live on the street or move and sleep from place to place in friends' houses, in markets or uncompleted structures etc. the street children phenomenon is called a worldwide challenge because, no nation across the world is exempted from the challenge of children neglect and parental un-readiness that results in abandonment and outright lack of care that drives such children into the street to find ways and means of fending for themselves.

According to statistics provided by the United Nations Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF), an estimated 100 million children live and work on the streets in developing countries of the world. Millions of children around the world survive in the street and only a few people or organizations are concerned about them. This passive attitude or response to the problem of street kids is also a problem that needs urgent attention, homelessness and kids in the street are yet to receive or draw the attention of the government.

A street kid is a term used for any child experiencing homelessness and lives on the street of a city, town or village. There is no definite definition of street kids, but many society, health practitioners and policymakers use the UNICEF definition of “any boys and girls, less than eighteen years, for whom “the street” (including unoccupied dwelling and wasteland) has become home and/or their source of livelihood, and who are inadequately protected or supervised, supervised or directed by responsible adults”. It therefore means that all children found on or on the street would fall into this category. Such children have been observed to spend more time on the street than at home. (UNICEF 2005)

In Nigeria there is a particular type of street kids known as the “area boys and girls.” These kids are school drop-outs and are known to provide unsolicited security and also act as praise singers to envisaged successful individuals or political big wigs living or passing through their “territories”. A study noted that these kids are at a high risk of getting involved in hard drugs or substance abuse which also increases the rate or level of violent crime in the city and society at large. Street kids are a common eyesore in major cities across the world but the problem is more prominent and rampant in developing and underdeveloped nations. Street kid challenge has gradually become an index capable of being used to measure the level of development in nations across the globe.

UNICEF categorized street kids into two. “Children on the Street and Children of the Street” (UNICEF 2005). Children on the street are those kids who have families and live with them but due to poverty and threat to their survival, are forced and exposed to the street to assume one role or the other in the street to hawk, beg, or engage in unskilled labour for a source of livelihood. While the “Children of the street are those kids who are in irredeemable positions and social dilemmas. They have no home, may have no families to go back to, they are solely responsible for themselves; this may be due to crisis, death of parents, rejection and poverty. It is sad to note that these kids living on the streets are expected leaders of tomorrow going through all the dehumanizing experiences and unbearable frustrations which turn them against society. The street stands for the public space and it is the place where children are not usually regarded, but life conditions drive some children to carry out activities that determine their survival. There are more street kids in poor, underdeveloped and developing countries whereas, the sight and population of street kids in developed countries are limited and under some relative control as a result of the citizens' welfare system of developed nations which at all times cater for and give attention and support to such children and their parents.

In Akwa Ibom State these street kids are known as “Utoto or Nditouba” They are children experiencing homelessness and live on the streets of the city. Such children find ready-made homes in uncompleted or untenanted buildings, under bridges and in wastelands in some cases. Some children perhaps are not homeless or without families, but live in environments where there is little or no protection or supervision from responsible adults. These kids feel that society, family, religion and most importantly government authorities have failed them because of the harsh conditions in which they find themselves. According to

Akpama, and Inaja, (2006), the inability of families to perform their primary responsibility of taking care of their kids has led to the uncoordinated activities of children, these have led to children fleeing homes to fend for themselves on the streets, an act, which in turn has generated armies of children on the streets. Many of these kids have made the streets their homes out of frustration either because they were abandoned at birth, orphaned, or disowned by their parents who have branded them as witches or wizards or also outright neglected by their parents. However some children choose to live in the street out of defiance, peer pressure, poverty or due to the psychological makeup of their parents. Regrettably, some children are on the street of Uyo metropolis to work and augment their family income. While on the streets in Uyo metropolis, these kids are made to face a lot of risks which are have been neglected by scholars, and it is the gap in literature which this research sought to fill. On this background, the main objective of this research was to examine the major risks faced by the street kids in Uyo metropolis, in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Challenges Faced by Street Kids

Ward and Seager (2010) carried out a sub-study concerning children within the Human Sciences Research Council study of street kids in South Africa. Three methodologies were used in the research – interviews, survey and census. In Johannesburg, twelve workers from different areas and three programs serving homeless kids were interviewed. In Cape Town, a focus group discussion was held with five directors from four service providers. These interviews assessed the service system environment. The findings in the article were that the number of kids on the streets is an indicator of the number of children living in poverty in South Africa. According to Ward and Seager (2010), street kids face a wide range of problems and have various needs that requires attention and support from society. Street kids are most especially harmed by harsh physical conditions, violence and harassment, labour exploitation, absorption into criminal networks and denial of their right to receive an education that will equip them to achieve a better life (Richter, 1991). UNICEF, 1992; Campbell and Ntsabane, 1995; Aderinto, 2000, highlighted the following challenges faced by street kids:

- i. **Lack of Basic Necessities and Amenities:** Street kids often lack access to necessities such as food, clean water, shelter, healthcare, etc, they also do not have regular access to proper hygiene facilities they may have to stay days or even weeks before taking their bath and this can lead to various health issues. Ward and Seager (2010).
- ii. **Education:** Street kids typically have little or no access to education. Lack of education further perpetuate the cycle of poverty and makes it difficult for them to break free from the streets.
- iii. **Exploitation and Abuse:** street kids are vulnerable to various forms of exploitation and abuse, including child labour, trafficking, sexual harassment and exploitation, physical violence and mental torture. They are most often forced into begging or engaged in illegal activities in order to survive (Crosson, 2008).
- iv. **Substance Abuse:** Many of the kids on the street turn to substance abuse as a way to cope with the harsh reality or as an escape to their problems. Drug and alcohol abuse further exacerbate their health and psychological condition.

- v. **Mental and Emotional Health:** kids living on the streets are exposed to trauma leading to mental and emotional health problems such as depression, anxiety. The effect of the past events which forced them to the street in the first place may have a lasting impact on the kid.
- vi. **Lack of Legal Protection:** The kids on the streets often lack legal protection and are more susceptible to being arrested, detained without trial, victimized by the security forces and legal system due to their vulnerability. The street is an unprotected environment and street kids are exploited.
- vii. **Stigmatization:** The society usually perceives street kids as difficult children who are out there to cause trouble. They are termed as uncontrollable and violent with little or no morals. They are seen to have lost all ability to feel emotions such as love and they turn into terrorists, the society is unsympathetic to the plight of the street kids.

Effects of Street Kids Phenomenon on Nigeria Society

All over Nigeria, it is a common sight to find children along the streets at all times of the day. These children sometimes engage in nefarious activities and hardly return home. The streets automatically have become an abode for such children. In the past, the presence of children on the street was very minimal but the problem of street children became aggravated after the Nigerian Civil War. The Civil War left tales of untold hardship on children who were made orphans or got separated from their parents through divorce or death. Many parents due to loss of the means of survival could not provide for their children who had no option but to take to the streets. Recently, with the emergence of the economic meltdown, children hawking, trading, begging or loitering have become the order of the day. UNICEF (2006) divided these kids into two coexisting categories. Children on the Street and Children of the Street. According to UNICEF (2006) Children on the street go there to trade or hawk goods for some hours during the day either for their parents, guardians or as hired hawkers. For most of these kids, they may have a home to return to at night while others simply keep some links with their families. Children of the Street on the other hand, are those who actually live and survive on the street on their own. For this category, the street is by all intent and purpose, a home for them. These children usually devise survival strategies which include stealing, use of violence, lying, cheating, among other anti-social activities. They loiter on the streets, motor parks and filling stations doing odd jobs, often fighting or pilfering other peoples' possessions. These street children assume different names such as Area boy (these include girls) Almajiris as in the north and are always there to be used by Politicians, demonstrators and mischief makers.

Several governments over the years have attempted to assist Nigerian Children – Akwa Ibom State in particular in different ways to no avail. The issue of assisting children to go to school is an age long phenomenon had not only attracted public concern but has also become a matter of priority to Government as well as International Organisations. For Instance, in the late 1950s, Chief Obafemi Awolowo introduced free education in the Western Nigeria in a bid to empower the children. Again, Denga (2002) pointed out that, in 1976, the Obasanjo led administration introduced the Universal Primary Education (UPE) to train Nigerian Children. Edim and Bisong (2002) informed that, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo in Sokoto State on 30th September, 1999, flagged off the Universal Basic Education (UBE) and on 27th May, 2002, the various States and Local Government Heads launched the UBE all

over the Federation. These lofty ideas were in a bid to pre-occupy and make every Nigerian child acquire at least basic education for future sustainability.

Also in 2009 the Godswill Obot Akpabio led government of Akwa Ibom State introduced a free and compulsory education not only for primary school but till senior secondary school. All these were in a bid to improve and encourage parents to send their wards to school and also allow those kids who are orphans the opportunity to be educated at least to senior secondary. Even with the free education, the situation has not seen any significant change. Apart from introducing the free education, Government imposed sanctions on erring children and parents who failed to be in school or send their children to school. Such sanctions included the arrest of school age children along the streets during school hours. In addition, Government provided free text books and reading materials to students in schools. Despite all these incentives and sanctions, the number of street kids of both the poor and the well to do in society keep increasing on daily basis. A cursory look at the cities shows a quantum number of kids roaming the street without returning home, some researchers opined that family poverty, deprivation, urban drift, unemployment and broken homes keep driving children into the street.

It has been recognized the fact that the definitions of a child, a youth and adolescent vary according to culture and custom. A child is considered as an individual younger than 18 years; a youth, as a young person who falls between the age of 15 and 24; and an adolescent as an individual in the state of development between the onset of puberty and maturity, from age 10 through 19 (UNICEF, 2001). From these definitions an overlap in the ages can be observed. Thus, the line demarcation between a child and a youth is not clear cut. As a result of this, children were not demarcated from the youth in this study.

Risks Associated with Street Kids Phenomenon

UNICEF (2001) defined a street child as any boy or girl who has not reached adulthood, for whom the street has become her or his habitual abode and / or source of livelihood, one who is inadequately protected, supervised or directed by responsible adults. Street kids are a common eye sore in major cities across the world but more prominent and rampant in developing and underdeveloped countries. It is gradually becoming an index used to measure the level of development in nations across the globe. What is clear from the above definition of a street kid is that such a kid leaves home to stay on the street and the street not only becomes the child's home but also the source of a living. Such a kid assumes full responsibilities on his or her own life. The Chairperson Nigeria Association of Women Journalists (NAWOJ) Akwa Ibom State Chapter stated in 2019 during a Premium Times round table in Uyo that there are too many children on the streets of Uyo. Despite the Child rights Act, enacted in 2008 in the state for the protection of the rights of children, many children from poor families are still on the streets. A lot of these homeless children engage in hazardous work on the street – for instance, dodging traffic as they sell goods to passing motorists. While many are engaged in legitimate work like car washing and watching, performing music and shoe shinning, others choose or are pushed into illegal activities including engaging in crime and theft, armed robbery, commercial sex or drug trade and trafficking, selling blood, or becoming drawn into organized begging (UNICEF, 2002). They are often among the most stigmatized urban dwellers and they constantly face abuse from other persons and harassment from the police. They are often arrested for crimes or simply for vagrancy, and can be trapped for long months in the slow moving bureaucracy of the

justice system, detained in conditions that violate their basic rights (UNICEF, 2002).

Street kids face extortion, child trafficking, kidnaping, theft, severe beatings, injuries /mutilation and poor health, no access to health care services, sexual abuse, stigmatization, rape, HIV and even death. While in police custody, they may be forced to pay bribes in order to be released. The girls may be coerced into providing sexual services to police officers in exchange for release, or may be raped and exposed to physical and sexual abuse, stress and mental health conditions, hunger and occasional hostile weather conditions (Cambell and Ntsabane, 1995). Most studies have focused on street kids in general, and a number of factors are usually considered as the reasons for their being in the street. These includes conflicts within the family; physical, emotional and sexual abuse; single parenthood, poor parenting, poverty, termination of education due to death of parents, child labour and peer pressure.

Street kids are further seen as either 'on the street' or 'of the street'. Children 'of the street' live and sleep on the streets in urban areas and streets are their homes, for example in Uyo metropolis, you see kids hawking sachet water, clean/wash windscreen of motorists at traffic points, hawk groundnuts, bitter kola and other wares, whereas children 'on the street' have their homes and only come to the streets to beg for money or hawk wares during the day and return home in the evening (Akpan and Oluabamide, 2010). The former group has no contact with family while the later lives with family. Our research and interviews are focused on both children 'of the street' and children 'on the street'. Kids living on the street despite their cultural differences represent a worldwide phenomenon. Examination of literature indicates that the background of street kids is remarkably similar. Even though, there are different countries and regions that have different structures of the existing policy on street kids (De brito, 2014). In South Africa discrimination of races is commonplace with street children. These children are seen as a threat to public safety. De brito (2014) write that for the children to be treated respectfully, an extensive protection system that protects all people is required in every community. Organizations that deal with human rights have to collectively bring up a recommendation concerning the dilemma of street kids.

Therefore, De brito (2014) writes that the organizations should have an involvement in creating a meaningful protection system. Many street kids come from structurally disadvantaged homes with poor living conditions. Parental loss through deaths or shortages of housing force kids onto the streets in order to survive (Shindi, 1998). According to Le Roux (2014), street life is an adaptive response to stress experienced by families living in poor conditions. The move onto the streets can represent a desire to take control and displace old values and habits with new ones. According to Nikku (2012), social workers work with children in need and provide services to ensure street kids right's. They are involved on a daily basis as to how to keep the children safe and which provider in society that can give the best tools for protection. As a social worker there is a need to work strategically as a civil society appeals to the protection of human rights, especially of minorities and street children that are often ignored by the government. Children's voices go often unheard and the right to affect the decision concerning them is ignored. Nikku (2012) mentions the importance for social workers to include the participation of children in practices, in terms of initial approaches on the street and concerning the rights of education and a place to stay.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Social Constructivism Theory

According to Lev Vygotsky (2015), a Russian Psychologist; social constructivism theory explains that learning in children occurs through social interactions and by the help of others. This theory emphasizes on the role of social interactions and cultural context in shaping individual's (child) understanding of the world. The social constructivism is a social learning theory which believes that the individuals are active participants in the creation of their own knowledge (Schreiber and Valle, 2013), Vygotsky believed that learning takes place primarily in social and cultural settings rather than solely within the individual. According to this theory; every function in the child's cultural development appears twice: first, on the social level 'between people' and later on, on the individual level 'inside the child'. Social constructivism theory focuses more on small groups. For instance kids learn primarily through interactions with parents, peers and teachers, whereas teachers stimulate and facilitate conversations through connecting the natural flow of conversation.

The fundamental concept of Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism is the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which emphasizes on the role of the instructor in an individual's learning ability. In relating the theory to street kids, social constructivism suggests that their experiences and identities are socially constructed through their interactions with their environment, including institutions and cultural norms. According to the theory street kids are not destined to live on the streets, instead their situations are shaped by various social factors such as poverty, family dysfunction, abuse, neglect, or limited access to education and social support systems. These factors contribute to their marginalized status and can lead to their involvement in street life. The social constructivism theory postulates that street kid's behaviours', attitudes and survival strategies are influenced by the social contexts in which they find themselves. They may form peer groups and subcultures that provides a sense of belonging and support within the street. They develop their own rules, norms and values which may differ from the mainstream society. Street kids may engage in activities such as begging, scavenging, hawking and other vices as a means of survival.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is located in the South-South geopolitical Zone of Nigeria, carved out from Cross River State in 1987 with its capital in Uyo and 31 Local Government Areas. The State is bordered on the East by Cross River State, on the West by Rivers State and Abia State, and on the South by the Atlantic Ocean. The state takes its name from the Qua Iboe River, which bisects the state before flowing into the Bight of Bonny. The population of the study comprised selected persons who are stakeholders on the street business in Uyo Metropolis. Two hundred and fifty (250) were selected.

The sample size of the study was determined from the population through the use of the Taro Yamene's formula. The formula is given by equation 1:

Equation 1:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size (minimum)

N = population size

e = margin of error

I = constant

Thus n = unknown

N = 250

e = 0.05

= 1

Thus : n = 153.84 = 154

The main instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire constructed under the guidance of the supervisor. The instrument was divided into two parts (A and B). Considering the nature of data collected, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) denoted by 'r', was adopted by the researcher for data analysis. The PPMC was used in testing the research hypothesis to ascertain the significant relationships that exist between the identified variables. The model for 'r' is given as in equation 2:

Equation 2:

$$r = \frac{n\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{(n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}}$$

Where:

n = the number of observation or perception of the population

x = respondents rating of the significant relationship between the variable under consideration

y = the total of each of the options rated multiplied by free point Likert scaling

r = Pearson product moment correlation coefficient

n = sample size

RESULT

Question: What are the major risks faced by street kids in Uyo Metropolis?

Table1: Percentage distribution of respondent's opinion on the major risks faced by street kids in Uyo Metropolis.

S/N	Options	Frequency	Percentage %
1	Abuse by the Adults	91	75.83
2	Disease	16	13.33
3	Substance Abuse	13	10.83
	Total	120	100

Researcher's Fieldwork (2023)

From the responses obtained in Table 1, 91(75.83%) of the respondents affirmed that the kids on the street face series of abuses mostly by the adults amongst them and also by the adults within the society; the girls among them face the risk of being raped, forced into child labour and other vices, pointing out that majority of the street kids in Uyo Metropolis face varied degrees of abuse and also 16 (13.33%) of the respondents said that the kids faces the risk of contracting different deadly diseases while on the street due to lack of personal hygiene, malnutrition and others; while the remaining 13 (10.83%) of the respondents agree that the kids while on the street abuse substances like solvent gum, and other hard drugs.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study found that most street kids are involved in substance abuse by making use of solvent based glue to take away the pangs of hunger, to relieve themselves of the cold temperature and cope with fear and frustration. The use of substance also gives them the courage to steal and engage in survival sex. It is a pragmatic response to a life characterized by hopelessness. Drug and solvent abuse is widespread as an escape from the reality of daily life of pain and struggle. The use of glue keeps children attracted to the streets (Oppong *et al* 2014). They become addicted to the glue, but the use of this substance causes a change in their personalities and most of them turn very aggressive and hostile to one another and to members of the public. The persistent use of solvent based glue can damage the liver, lungs and brain and can ultimately lead to sudden death of the kid.

The study also found that Street kids dwell in an environment of hostility. They are neglected by members of the public and they often lack proper parental guidance. According to Eriksen and Mulugeta (2016) claims that people raise children differently. They are usually perceived as difficult children who are out to cause trouble. They are stigmatized and termed as uncontrollable and violent with little or no morals. They often face abuse from others and harassment from the police, arrested for a crime they may not have committed, detained in conditions that violate their basic rights (UNICEF, 2002). Street kids face extortion, child trafficking, kidnaping, severe beatings, mutilations and poor health. Therefore, the public may not be able to identify with those who live on the street. The kids express their lack of treatment and support they get from their families on the streets; they share their experiences which often prove to be similar.

Finally, the study discovered that there are several needs and problems affecting the lives of street kids, according to Ward and Seager (2010), street kids face a wide range of problems and have various needs that require attention and support from society. The street kids are most especially harmed by harsh physical conditions, violence and harassment, exploitation, absorption into criminal networks and denial to education that will equip them to have a better life. Prominent among their needs are basic amenities of food, shelter, water, healthcare, educations, skill acquisition, legal protection and stigmatization and the society is unsympathetic to the plight of the street kids.

CONCLUSION

The phenomenon of street kids in any society is surrounded with many complex issues one that needs adequate attention from government, civil society and non-governmental organizations, because of its importance and implications on the larger society, especially when most of the representations of these kids are downright negative. It is important to approach the issue of street kids with empathy and a long-term perspective, recognizing the unique circumstances and challenges they face. Sustainable solutions should aim to provide these children with opportunities for education, skill development and social integration, ensuring they have a chance to lead fulfilling lives as productive members of society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher made the following recommendations;

1. Government should establish and enforce child protection laws that prioritize the rights and well-being of street kids. This includes providing safe shelters, rehabilitation programs, and access to healthcare and education tailored to their specific needs.
2. Government need to prioritize the development and implementation of comprehensive social welfare programs aimed at addressing the root causes of child vulnerability. This includes initiatives to alleviate poverty, provide access to education, healthcare, and affordable housing and support families in crisis.

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